

Observational Study of Pulmonary Function Test in Patients of Thalassemia Major in a Tertiary Care HospitalDeep Kariya¹, Alpa Parekh², Dimple Patel³, Chandan Narwani⁴, Dhaval Bhatt⁵¹Junior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, GMC Bhavnagar²Associate professor, Department of Pediatrics, GMC Bhavnagar³Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, GMC Bhavnagar⁴Pediatric Allergist & Assistant professor, Department of Pediatrics, GMC Bhavnagar⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Dr. N.D. Desai Faculty of Medical Science and Research, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Beta Thalassemia is hemolytic disease requiring regular blood transfusion which causes iron deposition in various organs of body in this study we study affect of iron deposition on lungs through pulmonary function test.**Aims & Objective:** To do pulmonary function test in Thalassemia major patients to assess the association between amounts of blood transfusion with results of pulmonary function test in Thalassemia major patients to assess the association between S. Ferritin level and with results of Pulmonary Function test in Thalassemia major patients.**Study Methodology:** This study is Observational study where pulmonary function test is carried out on 40 patients of Thalassemia major receiving blood transfusion and various results of test are compared and with pearson correlation results were obtained.**Results:** The correlation of pulmonary function test parameters of Thalassemia children between the BMI, Hemoglobin, S. Ferritin and chelation therapy were statistically not significant. Meanwhile, correlation of FEV1% with age and number of blood transfusion were statistically significant Remaining parameters of PFT were not significant between age and Number of Blood transfusion.**Keywords:** Pulmonary Function test, Thalassemia major, Blood transfusion.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

β -thalassemia major is an inherited, transfusion dependent chronic anemia which is caused by decreased production of β -globin chains required for formation of hemoglobin. As a result of this free α -chains accumulate in the RBCs and leads to the destruction of majority of the erythroid cells in the bone marrow.

Ineffective erythropoiesis, reduced hemoglobin synthesis, and short lifespan of erythrocytes in these patients lead to tissue hypoxemia and severe anemia. This can be partially corrected by maintaining the level of pre-transfusion Hb around 9.5-10.5g/dL by regular blood transfusions. Owing to their early effect on survival, extensive studies have been conducted on heart and liver dysfunction. However, lung dysfunction has never been adequately focused upon and remains to be one of the least understood complications.

Although it does not produce any symptoms and is not the most significant clinical manifestation of thalassemia, reduction in pulmonary volumes has been reported in most studies conducted in β -thalassemia patients. Varied abnormalities have been reported and these include restrictive lung disease, obstructive airway disease, impaired diffusing capacity of lung for carbon monoxide (DLCO). [1-7]

However, the physiologic basis of this is still not clearly known and many theories have been put forward by various investigators. Hence authors aimed to study the effect of iron deposition on lungs in children with β thalassemia.

Materials and Methods**Study Design:** Observational study**Study Period:** 6 months (Dec 2020-June 2021)

Study Setting: The study was conducted in association with confirmed diagnosis of β thalassemia major and having regular transfusion at department of pediatrics at Government hospital, Bhavnagar.

Sample Size: 40 β thalassemia major pediatrics attending department of pediatrics

Method of Collection of Data

Inclusion Criteria:

- Thalassemia major patient
- Age Group 6-12 years
- Receiving blood transfusion on regular basis for more than 1 year
- Taking regular iron chelators like desferrioxamine and oral deferasirox or deferiprone for more than 1 year

Exclusion Criteria: Any patient having existing pulmonary condition

Methods:

Children who fulfill the inclusion criteria for the study were selected. Informed consent was obtained from parents of all patients. Details such as age, sex, age at diagnosis, blood transfusion, duration of iron chelation therapy, pre transfusion haemoglobin level, mean ferritin level over preceding one year and physical examination findings were recorded on a proforma.

The study will be a hospital based observational study done at Sir T Hospital Bhavnagar. Informed Consent is taken from the parents of all patients included in the study after explaining the entire

study and thoroughly analyzing the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Spirometry will be performed on patient in sitting position with proper comfort and loosening tight cloths. Child will be instructed to take a full breath in and blow the air out as hard and fast possible

Pulmonary function tests were done using RMS Helios 401. Following parameters were recorded in the spirometry - Forced vital capacity (FVC), Forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1), Ratio of forced expiratory volume in 1 second to forced vital capacity (FEV1/FVC), Peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR), and Mid peak expiratory flow (PEF25%-75%). Pulmonary function tests were done three times, and the best values will be taken for the study. Serum ferritin levels were estimated by chemiluminescent immunometric assay. Haemoglobin estimation was done by Beckmen Coulter machine using cyanmethaemoglobin automated method.

Statistical Methods:

Descriptive statistics- Mean, median and standard deviation were used to compare the various quantitative parameters such as FVC, FEV1, FEV1/FVC, PEF25%-75%, PEFR and serum ferritin. Pearson's Correlation analysis was used to correlate various pulmonary function test parameters with serum ferritin levels, total amount of blood transfusion received and duration of chelation therapy. Probability value of less than or equal to 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Age Distribution of Patients

Age in years	Number of patients
6.-8.0	15 (37.5%)
8.0-10	11 (27.5%)
10.0-12	14 (35%)
Total	40 (100%)
Mean Age (yrs)	9.42 ± 1.87

Figure 1: Age Wise Distribution

In the present study, it was found that the age of the children ranged between 6 yrs to 12 yrs, with a mean age of 9.42 ± 1.87 yrs. In addition, 15 (37.5%) was the highest patients in 6-8 age group followed by 11 (27.5%) of the patients from 8.1-10 yrs age group.

Table 2: Gender Distribution of Patients

Gender	Number of patients
Male	23 (57.5%)
Female	17 (42.5%)
Total	40 (100%)

Figure 2: Gender Wise Distribution

In the present study, of the 40 children, 23 (57.5%) were males and the remaining 17 (42.5%) were females. Moreover, the male: female ratio was 1.35:1.

Table 3: Pulmonary Function Tests in Thalassemia

Pulmonary function	No of patients (N=40)
FVC	80.12 ± 16.41
FEV1	71.92 ± 14.11
FEV/FVC	89.30 ± 18.77
FEF ₂₅₋₇₅	79.2 ± 32.65
PEFR	91.17 ± 12.20

Figure 3: Pulmonary function test

In the present study, Percentage predicted of FVC and FEV1 was proportionately reduced with the mean values of $80.12 \pm 16.41\%$ and $71.92 \pm 14.11\%$ respectively.

FEV1/FVC of the group in this study was >0.7 (70% of predicted) (mean $89.30 \pm 18.77\%$) for all subjects indicating a non-obstructive pattern of

PFT. Values were almost similar among boys and girls. Among the 40 thalassemia major children subjected to PFT, 72.5% (29 out of 40) were found to abnormal pattern including (17 (42.5%) restrictive pattern; 8 (20%) obstructive pattern and 4 (10%) mixed pattern) and the remaining 11 (27.5%) were normal.

Table 4: Biochemical Parameters Wise Distribution

Biochemical Parameters	No of patients (N=40)
Hemoglobin (gm%)	
<10 gm%	13 (32.5%)
> 10 gm%	27 (67.5%)
Mean Hb	10.45 ± 0.92
Serum ferritin ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	
< 2500 $\mu\text{g/L}$	25 (62.5%)
> 2500 $\mu\text{g/L}$	15 (37.5%)
Mean Serum Ferritin($\mu\text{g/L}$)	2675.32 ± 1811.11

Figure 4: Biochemical parameters

In the present study, 13 (32.5%) of the patients were found anemia with mean hemoglobin of overall was 10.45 ± 0.92 gm/dL. In addition serum ferritin level proportionally reduced as <2500 in 25 (62.5%) patient with mean level of ferritin was 2675.32 ± 1811.11 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Table 5: Chelation Therapy Wise Distribution

Chelation therapy	No of patients (N=40)
Duration of Chelation	
< 5 years	23 (57.5%)
> 5 years	17 (42.5%)
Mean Chelation years	4.65 ± 2.07

Figure 5: Chelation therapy

In the present study, 23 (57.5%) from < 5 years have received chelation therapy then 17 (42.5%) of patients > 5 years. The mean chelation therapy was 4.65 ± 2.07 years.

Table 6: Blood Transfusion Wise Distribution

Blood Transfusion	No of patients (N=40)
Blood Transfusion (n)	
< 50	02 (05%)
50-100	7 (17.5%)
> 100	31 (77.5%)
Mean blood Transfusion	146.2 ± 57.47

Figure 6: Blood Transfusion

In the present study, it was found that mean blood transfusion found as 146.2 ± 57.47 in thalassemia pediatric patients. Hence, Blood transfusion was mostly higher found 31 (77.5%) of patients as > 100 number of BT.

Table 7: Gender Wise Distribution

	Male (n=23)	Female (n=17)	P value
Mean Age	9.73 ± 1.93	9.00 ± 1.76	0.2274
PFT Parameters			
• FVC	81 ± 16.78	78.94 ± 16.32	0.7000
• FEV1	70.04 ± 12.66	74.47 ± 15.91	0.3328
• FEV/FVC	89.43 ± 15.32	89.11 ± 23.15	0.9043
• FEF ₂₅₋₇₅	76.47 ± 32.81	84.35 ± 32.10	0.4533
• PEFR	91.43 ± 9.43	90.82 ± 12.46	0.8609
Biochemical Parameters			
• Hemoglobin	10.49 ± 0.92	10.40 ± 0.96	0.7656
• S. Ferritin	2655.95 ± 1782.07	2701.52 ± 1904.56	0.9389
Chelation therapy years	5.21 ± 2.30	3.82 ± 1.42	0.0342
Number of BT	154.65 ± 60.94	134.76 ± 51.84	0.2845

In the present study, due to correlation between gender and other parameters such as age, BMI, PFT parameters, Hemoglobin, Serum ferritin and Number of Blood transfusion were statistically not significant ($p > 0.05$). However, chelation therapy years was found statistically significant between gender (male vs female) distribution. (5.21 ± 2.30 years vs 3.82 ± 1.42 ; $p = 0.0342$)

Table 9: Correlation of PFT with Other Parameters

	FVC	FEV1	FEV/FVC	FEF ₂₅₋₇₅	PEFR
Age					
• Pearson Co-relation	-0.166	-0.305	-0.168	0.201	-0.015
• P value	0.305	0.036	0.030	0.213	0.929
S. Ferritin					
• Pearson Co-relation	-0.107	-0.092	0.175	0.171	-0.101
• P value	0.511	0.572	0.279	0.290	0.537
Chelation therapy					
• Pearson Co-relation	0.017	-0.115	-0.148	0.060	-0.062
• P value	0.917	0.480	0.363	0.713	0.705
Number of BT					
• Pearson Co-relation	-0.024	-0.362	-0.073	0.127	0.207
• P value	0.884	0.022	0.655	0.443	0.200

In the present study, the correlation of pulmonary function test parameters of Thalassemia children between the S. Ferritin and chelation therapy were statistically not significant. Meanwhile, FEV1% have found age and number of blood transfusion were statistically significant as ($r = -0.305$; $p = 0.036$) and ($r = -0.362$; $p = 0.022$) respectively, then FEV1/FVC have found age was statistically significant as ($r = -0.168$; $p = 0.030$). Remaining parameters of PFT were not significant between age and Number of BT ($p > 0.05$).

Table 10: Correlation of Serum Ferritin with PFT

Serum Ferritin	FVC	FEV1	FEV1/FVC	FEF ₂₅₋₇₅	PEFR
0-1500 µg/L	85.33 ± 20.14	75.08 ± 13.35	80.83 ± 18.92	75.08 ± 32.30	97.0 ± 8.73
1500-3000 µg/L	78.5 ± 15.41	72.18 ± 13.39	92.06 ± 14.11	83.5 ± 35.51	87.37 ± 8.44
3000-4500 µg/L	69.75 ± 16.37	61.75 ± 18.19	94.25 ± 25.27	56.75 ± 29.81	85.25 ± 11.35
> 4500 µg/L	80.75 ± 11.15	71.75 ± 15.06	94 ± 14.27	89.75 ± 25.04	93.0 ± 19.65
P value	0.408	0.457	0.239	0.366	0.141

In the present study, It was found that the serum ferritin correlation with PFT parameters which was not statistically significant as (FVC; $p = 0.408$, FEV1; $p = 0.457$, FEV/FVC; $p = 0.239$, FEF₂₅₋₇₅; $p = 0.366$, PEFR; $p = 0.141$).

Discussion

Beta thalassemia results from the abnormal synthesis of the β -chain hemoglobin; thus it usually starts to manifest as early as 4-6 months of prenatal life

during the switch from HbF to HbA. These patients are sustained only by repeated blood transfusions, which improve the anemia and reduce the skeletal deformities associated with excessive erythropoiesis. With transfusions alone, survival into second or third decade is possible, but gradually iron overload develops. Unless patients are treated aggressively with iron chelators, cardiac failure from secondary hemochromatosis commonly occurs and often causes death in the second and third decade of life.

Hardly any respiratory symptoms are seen in patients with Thalassemia Major (TM) despite the deposition of iron in the lungs. Most patients of Thalassemia major are still not on hyper transfusion regimen and/ or regular chelation in India. Theoretically, the lungs are also at major risk of damage secondary to iron overload. Hence, the present study was undertaken to record the frequency of pulmonary dysfunction in children suffering from Thalassemia major. Lung function has been studied in patients of Thalassemia major using various tests.

The commonest PFT done is Spirometry. FVC, FEV1, FEV/FVC, FEV (25%-75%), PEFR, TLC and Residual volume (RV) are among the lung volumes and capacities studied.

Apart from this the universally measured value is Serum Ferritin, to assess the extent of hemosiderosis and the efficacy of chelation therapy.

Summary

- (37.5%) was the highest patients in 6-8 age group followed by (27.5%) of the patients from 8.1-10 yrs age group with mean age of 9.42 ± 1.87 yrs.
- (57.5%) males were predominantly higher than (42.5%) of females. Moreover, the male: female ratio was 1.35:1.
- Mean weight and height were of present study was 31.17 ± 4.70 kg and 137.12 ± 6.50 cm respectively. In addition, Mean BMI was 16.59 ± 3.16 kg/m².
- Percentage predicted of FVC and FEV1 was proportionately reduced with the mean values of 80.12 ± 16.41 % and 71.92 ± 14.11 % respectively. FEV1/FVC of the group in this study was >0.7 (70% of predicted) (mean 89.30 ± 18.77 %)
- (72.5%) were found to abnormal PFT pattern including ((42.5%) restrictive; (20%) obstructive and (10%) mixed pattern) and the remaining (27.5%) were normal.
- (32.5%) of the patients were found anemia with mean hemoglobin of overall was 10.45 ± 0.92 gm/dL.
- Serum ferritin level proportionately reduced in (62.5%) from <2500 µg/L patient with mean level of ferritin was 2675.32 ± 1811.11 µg/L.
- (57.5%) from < 5 years were received Chelation therapy then (42.5%) of > 5 years. The mean chelation therapy was 4.65 ± 2.07 years.
- Mean blood transfusion found as 146.2 ± 57.47 in thalassemia pediatric patients.
- correlation between gender and other parameters such as age, BMI, PFT parameters, Hemoglobin, Serum ferritin and Number of Blood transfusion were statistically not significant. ($p>0.05$) However, chelation therapy years was found statistically significant be-

tween gender (male vs female) distribution. (5.21 ± 2.30 years vs 3.82 ± 1.42 ; $p=0.0342$)

- The correlation of pulmonary function test parameters of Thalassemic children between the BMI, Hemoglobin, S. Ferritin and chelation therapy were statistically not significant. Meanwhile, FEV1% have found age and number of blood transfusion were statistically significant as ($r=-0.305$; $p=0.036$) and ($r=-0.362$; $p=0.022$) respectively, then FEV1/FVC have found age was statistically significant as ($r=-0.168$; $p=0.030$). Remaining parameters of PFT were not significant between age and Number of BT ($p>0.05$)

Conclusion

- Following conclusion can be drawn from the study:
- None of the patients in my study showed any signs of pulmonary dysfunction In present study functional evaluation showed small airway disorder suggestive of air trapping.
- Hence in my study pulmonary dysfunction can be due to iron overload, Quantity of Blood transfusion, inadequate use of chelation. Probably the chronic iron deposition in form of ferritin and free iron might be main mechanism for oxidative damage.
- Lung can be a site of organ damage, and alteration of pulmonary function can be seen even in well-chelated TM patients. The respiratory system should be evaluated annually by PFTs even in asymptomatic patients to prevent pulmonary sequelae. Patients with abnormal PFT should be re-evaluated for compliance of chelation therapy and transfusion program.

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